

***‘Linguistic Shrapnel’*: Inner Speech in Borderline Personality Disorder and its Relevance for Self-Familiarity. A Philosophical Review**

Abstract:

This paper sheds light on the role of inner speech and self-talk in Borderline Personality Disorder (BPD) by providing a literature review of existing empirical studies on related phenomena. Building on these insights, it explores how processes of linguistic self-relation may affect an individual’s sense of self, notably self-familiarity. More specifically, it examines how processes of inner speech contribute to the genesis and sustainment of key psychological phenomena associated with BPD, which likely manifest as experiences of self-estrangement and hinder the development of a stable sense of self. First, I review the empirical literature on BPD, providing an overview of insights into intrapersonal dialogicality, auditory verbal hallucinations, inner speech and self-talk in BPD. Second, I then connect these empirical results with a philosophical notion of self-familiarity by exploring how linguistic processes in one’s experience of self, world, and others can significantly challenge or even undermine the development and sustainment of self-familiarity. By understanding how overt or covert dialogues within oneself may support or disrupt self-familiarity, I suggest, it becomes evident that linguistic self-relation is a critical area for therapeutic change and recovery in BPD.

Keywords: inner speech, internal dialogue, self-talk, intrapersonal plurality, phenomenology, self-familiarity, narrative self, borderline personality disorder

Introduction

Borderline Personality Disorder (BPD) is one of the most challenging mental health conditions and is characterized by a triad of instability: first, in the regulation of emotions, affect, and impulses; second, in self-image and self-experience; and third, in relationships, including one’s experience of and interactions with others (American Psychiatric Association 2013, 663). A central element in this context is a profound sense of unfamiliarity with oneself. Those affected often report a tense, diffuse, or even absent sense of self, which is expressed in unclear self-

images and inconsistent self-concepts. The opacity of self is sometimes also manifest in a puzzlement about one's own feelings and emotions. Emotions are often not recognized or fully comprehended, leaving individuals feeling bewildered, frustrated, and ultimately overwhelmed by the processes of life that elude their understanding. Not infrequently, this leads individuals with BPD to struggle in discerning the roles they occupy in their own lives and in recognizing how they contribute to the very experiences they undergo.

In this article, I explore how linguistic processes such as inner speech and self-talk may play into the challenges associated with a vague and unstable sense of self. Inner speech typically refers to linguistic processes or activities in which a person talks to themselves or to imagined others silently, without producing audible sounds or hearing voices in the strict auditory sense. Self-talk, by contrast, may include both inner speech and overt utterances directed at oneself – such as when one says out loud, “You can do it.”

In the last years, inner speech has been identified as an important factor across different mental health conditions (Alderson-Day & Pearson 2023, Alderson-Day et al. 2018, Brinthaupt et al. 2020, Łysiak 2019, McCarthy-Jones & Fernyhough 2011, Lin Toh, Thomas & Rossell 2015). Alterations in the experience of inner speech and the use of self-talk have been observed, particularly in the context of schizophrenia and autism spectrum disorder (ASD), affecting self-experience, self-other relatedness, affective self-regulation, general cognitive functioning, and thought processes, among others (Morin, El-Sayed & Racy 2015, Brébion et al. 2016, Petrolini, Jorba & Vicente 2020, Williams, Peng & Wallace 2016, Tsang et al. 2021). Given that BPD shares significant overlap in clinical presentation with both the schizophrenia spectrum and ASD, it is not unlikely that inner speech and self-talk also play a role in BPD, particularly in how a person relates to their own experiences and self.

However, in discussions of selfhood in BPD, the linguistic aspects of inner experience have so far not received the attention they deserve. The primary aim of this article is to take a first step toward filling this gap by reviewing existing empirical evidence in the clinical literature on BPD and by illustrating the relevance of self-talk for understanding the struggles with the sense of self that individuals with BPD often face. To do so, I examine the existing evidence through the lens of a notion of *self-familiarity*, which I introduce and develop through a discussion of philosophical approaches to selfhood.

I will suggest that self-familiarity is not merely an epistemic acquaintance with oneself in terms of knowing a set of narrative facts or being aware of a narratively constituted, crystallized, and

stable identity. Rather, it involves a practical capacity to cultivate a feeling of being at one with oneself, even as one's self-understanding is constantly in need of revision in light of ever-changing situations and transformative events. On this account, self-familiarity includes the practical sense of being able to re-establish a sense of self in such a way that one feels at home with oneself even when certain narrative identities are questioned or cannot be upheld. Accordingly, I will propose that self-familiarity entails a specific kind of confidence in one's ability for *self-familiarization*.

Drawing on the notions of self-familiarity and self-familiarization will allow me to formulate a framework for exploring how certain styles of inner speech may contribute to and underlie the struggles with self-experience observed in BPD. The general idea applied to BPD is that phenomena of inner speech are relevant to the processes of self-familiarization, and that when the latter are disrupted, difficulties in developing and sustaining a sense of identity ensue.

The first part of the paper reviews the clinical literature on dialogical and linguistic phenomena in BPD. The second part discusses self-familiarity and self-familiarization and, drawing on the empirical evidence, explores how self-talk in BPD may impinge on the process of self-familiarization. I conclude by suggesting that inner speech can also be considered a locus of change and thus provides an opportunity for individuals to develop, intensify, or strengthen feelings of self-familiarity.

1. Inner speech and self-talk in BPD: insights from empirical evidence

Language undoubtedly plays a central role in the psychological structure of the individual. It grounds how we experience meaning and is crucial in making sense of the world. Language also influences how we interact with others, and how we perceive people, the world, and ourselves. It is evident that our connection to others relies heavily on verbal communication. Less clear, however, is the extent to which linguistic processes also shape how we relate to ourselves.

Most people are familiar with the linguistic processes of inner experience from moments of reflecting on their own thoughts, impulses, or emotional tendencies. In such moments, it can be beneficial to engage in self-talk, whether spoken aloud or as silent inner speech. This speech need not always be actively performed, nor does it necessarily involve a deliberate reflective act. Even pre-reflective experience is likely to be marked by verbal moments in which linguistic elements passively emerge (Fossa & Pacheco, 2022). These internally experienced units of language often carry a strong sense of passivity—for example, when one feels warned in linguistic form by

oneself or by remembered or imagined others, as in verbal thoughts like “Not this way!” or “Don’t do that!” Self-talk, whether spoken aloud or silently as inner speech, can take many forms: from isolated sentence fragments to extended conversational sequences in which different voices of the self engage in dialogue. In such dialogues, individuals may experience themselves as the speaker, the listener, or both at once (Hurlburt, Heavey & Kelsey 2013). The following paragraphs in this section will present discussions and findings on various phenomena of self-talk in the context of Borderline Personality Disorder (BPD).

1.1 Inner plurality and an individual’s different ‘voices’

Individuals with BPD often experience marked instability in their sense of self, expressed in fluctuations of identity, emotions, desires, and goals. Such instability may lead to an overidentification with specific roles—such as parent, professional, or close friend—for limited periods of time (Schmidt & Fuchs, 2021). However, these individuals may later feel exhausted or overwhelmed by the limitations of these roles, as they only represent narrow aspects of their personality. The resulting tension often arises from the discomfort of a currently attained identity failing to encompass aspects of oneself that remain unintegrated. These unintegrated aspects hinder the formation of an overarching sense of self that connects the various roles an individual assumes in different life contexts. This experience of fragmentation frequently contributes to an inner sense of chaos (Fuchs 2007).

To better conceptualize these fluctuations and the lack of integration often seen in BPD, various theoretical models emphasize the inherent plurality of the self. The *Multiple Self States Model* (Ryle, Leighton & Pollock 1997), *Dialogical Self Theory* (Hermans & Kempen 1993, Hermans 2001), and the *Assimilation Model* (Stiles et al. 1990) all propose the idea of “multivocality” (Elliott & Greenberg 1997, 225) which suggests that a person’s identity is composed of multiple aspects or ‘voices’ that represent diverse facets of the self. These voices not only interact with the external world but also engage in an ‘internal dialogue’, as these models describe it.

This multivocal approach highlights the complexity of the self, offering a framework for understanding the inner experiences of individuals with BPD and their struggles with identity integration. In a study, Ryle (1997) identified six different states that were common in a sample of 20 individuals with BPD by analyzing descriptions of states they experienced. These involved states of feeling like the *ideal* version of oneself, *rage*, being a *powerless victim*, *angry victim*, a *coping state* characterized by a sense of being able to control others, and a *zombie state*. Ryle (2007) confirmed the distinction between different self-states and extended that list. Osatuke &

Stiles (2006) examined what they call “sub-communities of voices” in BPD: different voices of an individual that represent prior experiences but that are not integrated into one shared intrapersonal community. They found that the interaction between the community and such voices can vary, with some of them being more or less dominant, processed, avoided, included in the central community, and relating to bigger or smaller aspects of a person’s experience. Säämänen and colleagues (2016) observed that the BPD features in an individual were positively associated with personality fragmentation in depressed in-patients. More recently, different studies have been conducted to show that psychological change in the context of psychotherapy in BPD is associated with a reorganization of how the different voices relate to each other (Mellado et al. 2022, 2023). Kramer and colleagues demonstrate how this can involve a transition “from a multivoice cacophony to a two-voice dialogue” (2016, 153).

This is not to say, however, that these theories aim to reduce the occurrence of voices per se. Osatuke (2011) demonstrates that even individuals without a formal diagnosis can experience intrapersonal polyphony, which may become evident to others through noticeable shifts in their spoken voice and its variations. That is, internal multiplicity is taken to be the normal case. Most, if not all, people, have quite diverse facets, character traits, or roles that cannot be enacted in their entirety all at the same time. They often produce the need for intrapersonal negotiation, integration, or prioritization when incongruent and conflicting parts of oneself resurface. The question, thus, is not so much *whether* intrapersonal polyphony exists but rather *how* it is structured and experienced, that is, how it ‘sounds’ to the person. While the mentioned studies provide solid empirical evidence of plurality within the self by identifying its different personal states, they give only a very rough sketch of how corresponding voices appear in subjective experience. It is also important to note that the term ‘voice’ is primarily used as a *metaphor* (Stiles, 2011), drawing on a linguistic or dialogical model to make sense of how we experience the world and relate to others—as well as to ourselves. The dialogical approach does not claim that the various states referred to as ‘voices’ necessarily manifest as self-talk—that is, in the form of linguistic thought, inner speech, or spoken words. They may well be subjectively experienced as volitions or emotional states—particularly in situations of inner conflict involving incompatible wishes or desires. Engel et al. (2024) have recently demonstrated how distinct self-states can be manifested objectively through an individual's embodiment. More broadly, the dialogical approach to internal plurality provides empirical support for the view that selfhood is structured through interacting self-poles, which relate to one another in conversational modes. The next section is devoted to subjective experiences in BPD that have an unequivocal linguistic character and concern the perception of speech in one’s head without external stimulus (David 2004): auditory verbal hallucinations (AVH).

1.2 Auditory verbal hallucinations in BPD

Auditory verbal hallucinations (AVHs) are typically conceptualized as experiences of voice-hearing—that is, they are often modeled on perception and regarded as passive phenomena, phenomenologically comparable to sensory perception, though not grounded in any actual external stimulus. Particularly in challenging mental health conditions, such as the schizophrenia spectrum, one’s own linguistic thinking can escalate to a more passively experienced quasi-perceptual phenomenon typically labeled as auditory verbal hallucination (Tsang et al. 2021; McCarthy-Jones & Longden 2015; McCarthy-Jones & Fernyhough 2011). Recent accounts have, however, questioned whether AVHs in schizophrenia should be conceptualized as *perceptual* phenomena, suggesting instead that they are better understood in terms of *beliefs* about perception (Humpston & Woodward 2024) or as *thought-voices* (Parnas, Yttri, & Urfer-Parnas 2024). Regardless of how exactly AVHs are best characterized phenomenologically, what matters is that they exhibit a predominantly *receptive* rather than a *performative* or *agential* quality. They are experienced less as something one actively does than as something one passively undergoes, yet they are not equivalent to perceptual experiences either.

While not all individuals diagnosed with BPD experience hallucinations, and those who do may encounter hallucination-like experiences referring to the various senses, AVHs are frequently reported among people with BPD. D’Agostino (2019) observed that roughly 50% of all BPD people experience AVHs. Niemantsverdriet and colleagues (2017) conducted telephone interviews with more than three hundred outpatients of which 27% reported AVHs. Several recent studies offer important insights regarding the phenomenology of AVHs in BPD. If hearing voices in BPD has traditionally been described as “pseudohallucinations” (Heins et al. 1990, Berrios & Dening 1996) or “quasi-psychotic thought” (Zanarini et al. 1990), owing to the idea that related phenomena are supposedly only of short duration, considerable evidence has been accumulated suggesting that AVHs in BPD and schizophrenia are in fact comparable regarding duration, frequency, degree of negative content, and their disruptive impact on a person’s life (Slotema et al. 2012, Tschoeke et al. 2014, Merrett et al. 2016, 2022, Strawson et al. 2022). In BPD, however, AVHs seem to be particularly emotion-laden and trauma-related, while in schizophrenia they tend to be associated with other delusional symptoms (Tschoeke et al. 2014).

It is noteworthy that AVHs, while qualitatively resembling more a receptive phenomenon, also often come with verbal activity of those hearing voices. For BPD, Merrett and colleagues (2022) found that roughly 88% of the BPD participants interacted with the voices they heard, responding

to them in conversational sequences. Interestingly, AVHs and interaction with them also occur in non-psychotic cases of BPD. This, for instance, is illustrated by Wallis and colleagues (2022) of ten persons with non-psychotic diagnoses of emotionally unstable personality disorder (EUPD, n=8) and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD, n=2) who have described their AVHs in the context of qualitative interviews.

To conclude, not all individuals with BPD experience AVHs. Those who do may do so in ways that are comparable to psychotic experiences in schizophrenia (be it more of a delusional or a hallucinatory kind) or in non-psychotic ways. Given that AVHs are also prevalent in the general population, where the phenomenology of hearing voices can take varying degrees of severity and manifest differently (Beavan, Read & Cartwright 2011), this supports a *continuum* view about hearing voices in BPD. In the next section, I present additional evidence from the non-psychotic end of the spectrum in BPD and focus on the individual's verbal activity—that is, on active responses to voices and the enactment of self-talk.

1.3 Self-talk in BPD

While there may be no empirical studies specifically addressing inner speech or self-talk in borderline personality disorder (BPD), internal monologues and dialogues nevertheless feature in the clinical literature on BPD in various ways. As the example of AVHs has shown, hearing voices in an almost perceptual manner can be deeply unsettling. The same holds true for the experience of verbal thoughts unfolding in one's mind without being of a hallucinatory nature.

This is so because, in BPD, individuals are prone to excessive self-criticism and self-punishment, which can take the form of negative self-talk. For instance, Koivisto and her colleagues (2021a), who conducted a qualitative study to examine the experience of change in BPD, have demonstrated the relevance of negative self-talk in BPD. They performed content-analyses of 40 group sessions of individuals undergoing psychotherapy (schema therapy) to determine which topics were among the most salient to emerge in the discussions between 8 people with BPD (Koivisto et al. 2021b). The most central issue was 'self-invalidation', which they consequently investigated in more detail. Among the three core categories that this analysis revealed, a self-critical and harsh attitude towards self proved as the most important one, voiced by all participants and relating to 82,4% of all self-invalidating expressions in the group discussions. Of these, 65,2% referred to self-invalidating self-observations or self-talk. One participant described it as follows: "It is as if I had a voice in my head telling me ... 'you never do anything right'. Somehow I feel this voice isn't even my own." (Koivisto et al. 2021b, 926) This study

corroborates other reports or descriptions of BPD that mention the prevalence of negative self-talk or voice-hearing that is not clearly diagnosed as AVH in BPD (Schie et al. 2024, Nath & Bhuva 2023, Francis et al. 2022, Baltzersen 2021, Saraiya et al. 2021, Harster et al. 2021, Kennett 2020, Haverkamp et al. 2017, Mosquera & Steele 2017, Mosquera et al. 2014, Freeman & Jackson 1996, Miller et al. 1993, Nehls & Diamond 1993). These observations also lend support to Linehan's (1993) influential dialectical-behavioral therapy, designed specifically for individuals with BPD. Linehan's approach underscores the importance of stopping or blocking "overt or covert verbal aggression," which may take the form of "hostile dialogues" directed against oneself or of "verbal attacks on the object of anger" (1993, 355).

The intrinsically distressing nature of negative self-evaluations in BPD becomes particularly evident when examining the relationship between self-talk and well-being. Empirical evidence across different psychopathologies and within the general population is heterogeneous. Some studies (d'Argembeau et al. 2011) have found that states of happiness are less characterized by inner speech, whereas others have observed a positive correlation between inner speech and happiness, along with a negative correlation between inner speech and sadness (Hurlburt & Akhter 2006). It is likely that these relationships are mediated by the structure and quality of self-talk involved in individual cases. Given the negative character of BPD self-talk, it is not surprising that inner speech is prone to contribute to suffering. This can be illustrated by the following verbalization of lived experiences of Amanda, a participant of group discussions led by Koivisto and her colleagues (2021b): "if I'm, say, in a cheerful mood... There comes the experience 'you failed in this' or 'you said this or that to somebody. ... This occurs particularly when I've just achieved something.'" (927) Sarah, another participant, agrees: "Exactly, it's particularly after those happy moments that the punitive parent's voice drags you down." (Koivisto et al. 2021b, 927) As these examples show, self-talk in BPD, being self-destructive, tends to generate negative affect rather than sustain happiness, even in situations that would otherwise provide reasons for contentment. It appears that the inner voice can itself take a dismissive stance toward the positive, as if to forestall the later intrusion of critical or self-reproachful voices (Freeman & Jackson, 1996). Negative self-talk in BPD, however, not only pops up as a damper to happiness. In fact, it often is also described as emerging in stressful times, exacerbating challenging experiences by turning inner speech into self-blame and self-punishment (Koivisto et al. 2021b, Mosquera et al. 2014, Nehls & Diamond 1993).

As these examples illustrate, negative self-talk is not only distressing in itself but also compounds challenges for individuals struggling with it by triggering additional symptoms and difficulties commonly associated with BPD (Nath & Bhuva, 2023). In other words, some features of BPD

may partly stem from and be exacerbated by intrusive and uncontrollable negative self-talk. Take, for instance, the following first-person report illustrating the disturbance through self-talk: “Later, my inner monologue has become more of a dialogue ... (.) ... (T)his is new and causes me a great deal of anxiety when it occurs.” (Edwards 2016, 148). The self-invalidations that result from negative self-talk have also been linked to low self-esteem and shame feelings which both are characteristic of BPD (Schie et al. 2024, Koivisto et al. 2022, 2021a,b). Saraiya and colleagues (2021) observed that shame self-talk is higher in BPD than in PTSD, illustrating the intensive pain associated with negative self-talk. Francis and colleagues (2022) investigated the lived experiences of mothers with BPD over the course of a mother-infant dialectical behaviour therapy and found that, while many aspects of the psychological situation had improved, shame self-talk tended to persist when it related to an individual’s personality.

Moreover, it seems that it is not only, or not necessarily, the *content* that induces feelings of shame. The following first-person description of voices, published in Koivisto (2021b), illustrates that it can sometimes be the very *form* or *quality* of negative self-talk itself that is experienced as undermining and potentially humiliating: “I’ve noticed that I still experience the punitive voices at the level of a child. They are exactly the same voices I was taught when I was young. I haven’t had the chance to outgrow them.” (Koivisto 2021b, 926).

Inner speech, then, can have a detrimental effect in BPD: not only by activating distressing emotions but also by shaping how individuals view themselves and the roles they play in relationships. Lived experience examples serve to illustrate the impact on selfhood: “I took the idea of *never good enough* to heart. Both real and perceived negative reactions transcended into self-talk and became the story of who I was.” (Baltzersen 2021, 77) With such an influence on self-views, inner speech may also trigger certain styles in self-regulation. The following dialogue between an interviewer who is a therapist and ‘Debbie’, a participant with BPD, serves as a further illustration. The dialogue is transcribed from an interaction as part of a workshop on cognitive-behavioral therapy. Asked about whether she ever tried to argue with the critical voices in her head, Debbie answers: “The noise gets louder and I begin to hurt myself.” (Freeman & Jackson 1996, 196)

Negative self-talk, which can involve other people’s voices and generally disturb a person’s psychological attunement to a situation, may also strain their relationships with others in various ways. If it is true that reactions from others can trigger processes of negative self-talk, this may also help explain the high levels of rejection sensitivity associated with BPD and its link to rage (Berenson et al., 2011). A better understanding of the workings of inner speech, then, may

contribute to explaining how social interactions can suddenly be disrupted by intensely negative emotions or moods, which often lead to interpersonal turmoil and difficulties. While many approaches explain over-critical inner voices as the internalization of past negative others or even hostile environments (Schie et al. 2024, Nath & Bhuva 2023), it is thus also likely that negative self-talk diffuses back into social interactions.

The case of Debbie illustrates potential cases of a more *direct* relationship between inner speech and interpersonal problems. When asked by the interviewer whether she typically argues with the critical voices, she answers: “I argue with John [her therapist] instead.” (Freeman & Jackson 1996, 194) The idea then is that people with BPD might start a fight with a real person rather than trying to sort out things with their inner voices. For instance, when an individual feels powerless against internalized others who may have become a pole of almost mechanically-arising and uninvited power of opposition, playing out inner tension and conflicts with real others may appear as an easier way of release. If the voices of the inner other are of a rigid kind, real others, more likely, might be more responsive to what an individual suffering from inner voices might do or say. That is, if an individual feels powerless against their *inner* voices representing self or others, exerting control over *real* others—which might resonate more strongly with one’s own actions—could seem appealing.¹

Another effect of negative self-talk on social interaction may be *indirect*. Self-invalidation through inner speech is a key mechanism for generating, maintaining, and perpetuating negative self-views. Negative self-views have been shown to hinder a person’s ability to form positive relationships (van Schie et al. 2024). It is likely, however, that internal dialogues not only affect social interactions via self-images. Internal dialogues can be considered as basic forms or structures of relating to others in general. Phenomenological thinkers have sometimes argued that the most fundamental dialogical relationships between *I and thou* underlie more complex forms of sociality and social interactions (e.g., León 2024; Meindl & Zahavi 2023). Inner speech may then be considered one important way in which the fundamental relationships between *I and thou* are constituted and played out (Arendt 2016). Thus, if these more basic and linguistic interpersonal structures are challenged, relating to other people in general will prove more difficult.

The previous aspects have demonstrated that negative self-talk is associated with other symptoms of BPD. Importantly, these associations are multi-directed. Apart from triggering other

¹ This dynamic might underlie some of the behaviours of people with BPD that are sometimes deemed indirect, manipulative, or destructive (cf. Schmidt 2021).

symptoms, self-talk sometimes resurfaces in response to discomfiting psychological phenomena and thus are evoked by other BPD symptoms. For instance, it has been described as a measure to navigate stress and to maintain some control in moments of crisis, which—though not a complete solution—can be perceived as helpful (Nehls & Diamond 1993). Others have observed self-talk also to be a measure of distraction individuals engage in when they feel the urge to hurt themselves (Rayner et al. 2021, Nee & Farman 2007). While sometimes initially intended as a way to mitigate and regulate certain affective and cognitive processes, it is likely that such attempts can—and also probably often—fail with critical and self-punitive voices taking over internal dialogues that have been instigated to get a hold on a situation.

Finally, self-talk in BPD has also been identified as an important locus of change. Given its significant impact on various dimensions of a person’s lived experience of the shared world, several approaches have emphasized the importance of modifying self-talk as part of the recovery process and as an active component of therapeutic treatment (Haverkamp et al. 2017; Koivisto et al. 2022; Harster et al. 2021; Linehan 1993). This is far from being a matter of merely reducing engagement in self-talk; rather than a quantitative modification, it involves a qualitative change that consists in using self-talk in such a way that it empowers individuals to self-regulate their thoughts, feelings, and behaviors (Kross et al., 2014).

2. Self-familiarity in BPD and the role of self-talk

In the first section, I discussed empirical findings on intrapersonal plurality, auditory verbal hallucinations, inner speech, and self-talk in BPD. While further empirical research is clearly needed to fully understand the nature and role of self-talk in BPD, I argue that existing insights already make valuable contributions to our understanding of core aspects of the disorder. Building on these findings, the aim of the second section is to explore how inner linguistic and intrapersonal dialogical processes shape self-experience. To conceptualize this, I first introduce the philosophical notion of self-familiarity, which I propose as a useful lens for understanding the challenges posed by the forms of self-talk observed in BPD. I then examine how these forms of BPD-related self-talk may undermine the development and continuity of self-familiarity, thereby contributing to difficulties in maintaining a coherent sense of identity.

2.1 Self in BPD: On the need to extend the narrative view

How do the linguistic phenomena observed in the context of BPD relate to selfhood, and can they help clarify why individuals with BPD often struggle with how they feel about themselves and

their sense of self that emerges from it? To assess this, it is important to be clear about the precise notion of selfhood at stake. In philosophy and psychology, there exists an abundance of competing concepts of self, and with them a plethora of conceptualizations of what kind of self-experiences are possible, which of them are more basic than others, and which are essential when we speak of difficulties with an individual's sense of self.

A commonly discussed distinction has been made between a basic notion of selfhood, or *minimal self*, and a *narrative self*, a more elaborate kind of self-awareness that comprehends a wider spanning horizon of a person's life including memory, habits, individual character traits, life goals, and an overall story of oneself (Zahavi 2015). Both notions have been employed in the context of mental health challenges. The notion of the minimal self has particularly been applied in discussions of self-disturbances in schizophrenia to conceptualize the severe feelings of alienation towards the own experiential process and its contents (Raballo et al. 2021; Sass & Parnas 2003; Zahavi 2001). In the significant majority of most non-comorbid cases of BPD, however, struggles with one's sense of self do not concern this basic form of self-awareness but rather the sense of self that refers to one's identity. Accordingly, the narrative self has been central to examining challenges in developing and maintaining a sense of identity in the context of BPD (Sterna, Fuchs & Moskalewicz 2025; Schmidt & Fuchs 2021; Schmidt 2020; Bortolan 2020; Køster 2017; Fuchs 2007).² The outcome of recent debates suggests that the lack of a clear self-concept in individuals with BPD stems from difficulties in establishing a stable self-narrative that a person could identify with. Associated with this is the idea that a more robust sense of self would typically serve as a scaffold for fostering a positive self-feeling, regulating disruptive emotional experiences, and improving interpersonal relationships by helping individuals develop internal validation rather than depending on others for reassurance.

While the notion of the narrative self has been helpful in elucidating the difficulties of maintaining a stable sense of self and their associations with other challenging experiences in BPD, the narrative view, as articulated so far, also has certain limitations, and open questions remain. One criticism of the narrative view has been voiced by arguing that narrative identity might not be the best criterion for defining the self-disturbance in BPD because there is nothing pathological per se in lacking a strong sense of a diachronic self (Gold & Kyratsous 2017). Drawing on Galen Strawson's (2004) well-known distinction between *episodics* and *diachronics*, as well as his broader criticism of the narrative self-view, the authors emphasize that individuals in the general population may not possess a clear narrative identity without suffering. They can

² Baptista et al. (2021) discuss whether BPD self-disorder could be explained by alterations of structures related to the minimal self but conclude that such attempt would face decisive limitations.

still live fulfilling lives without feeling that they are missing anything. I might remember the experiences of my past life—for instance, what it was like to be a student, what the student-me did, wanted, and felt—yet still feel today that I am no longer that person. Although I remain psychologically connected to the student-me, I may now experience myself as someone else, distinct from that past self in an important way. Still, I might feel perfectly fine—without any painful sense of fragmentation.

However, as argued in previous work, a narrative account of selfhood can still contribute to our understanding of BPD—notably because people experiencing BPD symptoms often *do* suffer from not having a stable and strong sense of who they are, and for them, developing a clearer narrative identity might actually matter (Schmidt & Fuchs 2021). Moreover, it is not only that individuals with BPD often long for a clearer narrative identity they can hold onto; in many cases, they also actively construct identities to make sense of specific situations and the overwhelming emotions involved—either for themselves or to navigate social interactions by enacting identity “masks”, as it were (Petrolini & Schmidt-Boddy 2025). Unlike in the case of Strawsonian “episodics”, these are attempts to feel and embody diachronic selves; yet they remain unsuccessful and often lead to confusion and emotional distress.

That said, while bearing in mind the significance of narrative processes for the sense of self in BPD, it might be wise to refrain from reducing BPD self-disturbance to an alleged lack of narrative self. One problem with the narrative approach is that it may place too much emphasis on a single coherent story and on the idea that one’s identity takes the shape of a protagonist of such a story.

For individuals with BPD, such a criterion may be overly demanding, potentially leading to frustration when they feel unable to achieve a high degree of narrative coherence. Moreover, it remains unclear whether individuals without BPD—or without any clinical diagnosis—who exhibit a relatively stable narrative identity truly rely on a single, central life story to ground their self-understanding. The fact that inner speech and intrapersonal plurality are common even among those who do not struggle with their sense of self suggests that self-stability does not primarily or exclusively depend on the coherence of one unified life narrative. Instead, one might take it that self-stability rather consists in the *familiarity* with a plurality of self-perspectives and a related kind of *trust* in oneself that one will be able to solve any conflict between different self-aspects. This involves tolerating insecurities about oneself, as well as ambivalence, where inner conflict may persist for some time. The capacity to bear intrapersonal plurality—and the inner fractures and tensions it can sometimes entail—has been identified as a central feature of a subject capable of thought, critical judgment, genuine self-determination, and empathy (Arendt,

2016). If that is on the right track, it follows that intrapersonal plurality ought not to be reduced or eradicated (Church 2021). Instead, it should be cultivated appropriately, serving as a source for a sense of self that does not rely on a monolithic and supposedly incorruptible narrative identity.

A second issue is closely related to this: we sometimes come to feel and think in different patterns about our lives and may oscillate between different interpretations without ever finally deciding on certain narrative issues. Although many people have a more or less consistent narrative about their lives, which may help them sustain a sense of who they are, it is likely that these very same people see their lives in a different light depending on changing moods, the people and situations they engage with, and other aspects of life's volatility. Often, what matters more than having a seemingly incorruptible sense of narrative identity is a fundamental trust in the process of identity formation—that is, trust that one will be able to integrate new experiences and evolving self-perceptions, to adapt one's narrative identity over time, and to remain affectively intact even when it is unclear who one is or when one's sense of identity shifts as life unfolds. Thus, the *process* of narration itself and its structure might be more important than the concrete *result* of the process: a certain narrative content. If that is true, I suggest that it might be important to also look at the process of identity formation and the role of narrative structures therein, rather than focusing too much on whether a stable narrative identity has crystallized in an individual or not.

This is supported by a third point and insight gained by looking at self-talk in BPD. As it turns out, individuals with BPD actually do sometimes experience stable narrative structures. However, these are rather negative and associated with emotional pain. For example, consider the case described above: individuals who report being haunted by an inner parental, punitive voice that attacks them whenever they feel genuine happiness or purpose, or someone who realizes that their identity as the listener of these voices remains that of a young child. These examples instead point to a pronounced, though immature and underdeveloped, sense of identity. People with BPD symptoms often report feeling trapped in recurring patterns, unable to discern any silver lining or prospect of change. In fact, some are more concerned with having to change, as they feel they are “not ready to change certain things, despite their detrimental effect on my life” (Edwards 2015, 38). Another quote by the same author illustrates that a considerable narrative knowledge may be prevalent: “All these people that called me ‘friends’ have each thrust the knife into my back and walked away. I take credit for my part in it.” (Edwards 2015, 60) Rather than a complete absence of narrative self-knowledge, individuals may develop a feeling “of being stuck in a process that is unstoppable” (Schmidt 2020, 211; cf. Sterna, Moskalewicz, Schmidt-Boddy & Fuchs 2025), precisely *because* some seemingly insurmountable narrative lines have crystallized. Consider also

the first-person report of Cappuccino (2022) who emphasizes: “In spite of having difficulties with a shifting self-image, I have never struggled with knowing who I am” (179)

This suggests that feelings of emptiness, self-instability, and chaos in BPD do not always—or, at least not exclusively—stem from a problem in the knowledge of narrative facts. Instead, it seems that sometimes the issue is more one of making sense of what one recognizes as a part of oneself, as coming to terms with one’s process rather than simply knowing it. Although several researchers have underscored affective aspects of the narrative self (Bortolan 2020; Breger 2017; Hogan 2011; Miall 1988), the notion has a tendency to evoke an epistemic focus, i.e., a focus on the awareness of one’s experiences and their meaningful organization in a coherent order spanning from the lived past through the present and towards the future. This epistemic focus, however, may risk overlooking the significance of *feeling* at one with oneself—that is, of being in harmony with who one is. Accepting what one knows about oneself as genuinely representing who one truly is might reach beyond the level of the narrative self. Some may be able to recount their life story and yet fail to find themselves within it, as if untouched by the narrative facts they acknowledge as true. In reflecting on one’s life, one may therefore experience estrangement and alienation rather than a sense of familiarity with who one appears to be.

For these reasons, and those outlined above, I suggest that difficulties with self-experience in BPD should not be examined solely through the lens of narrative selfhood or a diminished narrative identity (cf. Køster 2022). This is not to imply that narrative processes are irrelevant, but rather that a feeling of being at one with oneself is a more complex phenomenon—of which narrative identity is only one dimension.³ In the following section, I introduce the notion of *self-familiarity* to broaden the perspective on selfhood in BPD. This concept will also serve to illustrate how self-talk in BPD contributes to the challenges individuals face in their experience of self and identity.

2.2 Self-familiarity: A philosophical notion

In the last section, I argued that the notions of the minimal and narrative self may not suffice to fully capture and comprehend the challenging self-experiences of individuals with BPD. I suggest

³ Køster (2017) and Gallagher (2023) suggest that narrative practices serve an integrative function, enabling individuals to connect different aspects of their experience that might otherwise feel unrelated or alien. While I agree, I believe it is crucial to examine the linguistic (and affective) structures involved in narrative processes in greater detail, as inner speech is likely a central medium for fostering narrative self-understanding (Rovetta, 2024).

that the notion of self-familiarity may offer a broader perspective. But what exactly is meant by self-familiarity?

First, I suggest that we draw on the philosophical literature to distinguish between two forms of self-familiarity: *immediate* and *mediated*. The notion of immediate self-familiarity refers to a basic form of self-awareness, often understood in similar terms as the minimal self—an immediate acquaintance with one’s own experience that underlies and enables the experience of any object. As Frank (2022, 280) notes, “objectual self-knowledge presupposes non-objectual self-familiarity.” Similarly, Fuchs (2017, 298), drawing on Zahavi’s work, argues that “being conscious implies a self-acquaintance or self-familiarity for which no act of self-identification is required.”

Zahavi himself uses the term rather sparingly and associates it with a thicker kind of self-awareness that is subject to changes: “On a slightly more robust reading, the for-me-ness and mineness of experience can refer to a sense of endorsement and self-familiarity, to the quality of ‘warmth and intimacy’ that William James claimed characterizes our own present thoughts. If this is what is meant by for-me-ness and mineness, I think it can be disturbed and perhaps even be completely absent.” (Zahavi 2015, 41)

This understanding of self-familiarity as something liable to change points to a mediated form of self-familiarity. As Køster (2022, 5) describes, “our sense of self-familiarity—our sense of feeling at home with ourselves—is not something static or given but a temporal structure relying on daily experiences of confirmation. Self-familiarity, in this respect, is a distributed phenomenon that cannot meaningfully be separated from my broader world-entanglement.” Hence, self-familiarity is not immediately given or intrinsic to experience; it is something that must be achieved, can be lost, and has to be regained over time—again and again. As he further writes, “it is not a direct possession, but sustained by and inseparable from the integrated web of constituents I daily use to recollect a sense of myself” (2022, 5). This also includes our relationships with close others, friends, and family, which are crucial for sustaining a sense of self-familiarity—a sense of who we are (Køster 2021). As life unfolds and relationships evolve, we are constantly called upon to appropriate the lifeworlds we inhabit—that is, to make them our own by meaningfully situating ourselves within the lives we lead, with all their shifting trajectories, uncertainties, aspirations, disappointments, and transformations. This process of appropriation is not a one-time act but an ongoing negotiation: it involves interpreting our place amid change, reconciling with loss, and reorienting ourselves in light of new circumstances. In doing so, we continuously work to maintain a sense of coherence and belonging.

But what exactly does it mean to be self-familiar in the mediated sense, how can we achieve it, and how does it relate to immediate self-familiarity? First, let me clarify that, by mediated self-familiarity, I understand a specific way in the organization of an individual's sense of self, i.e., how it is formally structured and the quality of self-experience that results from it. To further spell this out, let me turn to Ratcliffe's (2025) notion of self-familiarity. He takes it to be

“an overarching sense that the various facets of our lives *do* hang together as a coherent, diachronically organized whole. It involves being able to move familiar routes through our biographies, anticipating that our memories will unfold in familiar ways, and evaluating our past in ways that are congruent with our current concerns.” (Ratcliffe 2025, 14)

While this description may sound like it amounts to a narrative approach oriented in constituting a diachronic whole, it refers to much more than a simple *knowing-that* but involves a *knowing-how* to navigate the different aspects of one's identity, the different experiences that relate to them, and the distinct modes in which they are presented and re-presented across time. Self-familiarity so-conceived “is a certain way of moving between the contents of our intentional attitudes—how our experience flows between perceiving, remembering, thinking, imagining, acting, and expecting in ways that involve confident anticipation and unproblematic fulfilment rather than a pervasive sense of anomaly, discrepancy, or surprise.” (Ratcliffe 2025, 16f.)

Ratcliffe's notion points to the practical abilities that are involved in having a stable narrative identity which not only concern the integration of past experiences in a coherent order but also includes the future-directed practical sense or self-confidence that “*we will be able* to continue moving around our lives in this fashion, that things will remain integrated as they continue to unfold” (Ratcliffe 2025, 17).

As I read—or, say, want to read—this proposal, this is not meant to suggest that self-familiarity, so construed, implies the sense that one's narrative identity is so stable and well worked out that one can confidently integrate whatever happens in the future into that particular identity. Instead, I want to suggest that it means being confident in one's ability to develop a new narrative identity if one's current sense of identity can no longer be upheld in light of future experiences. Thus, self-familiarity, as I envision it, is not simply the confidence that one's current narrative identity, as it is understood in a given moment, will persist no matter what happens, but rather the confidence that, whatever happens, one will find a way to develop a sense of identity that remains meaningful to oneself.

Self-familiarity, in my understanding, thus goes beyond our narrative knowledge and its specific contents; it also concerns the practical sense of one's ability for *self-familiarization* as an ongoing process. Such a practical sense is generally grounded in prior experiences of successfully forming one's identity amid various challenges. As Jaspers writes: "The life of the mind does not proceed in a continuous manner; rather, the phases of its development are interrupted by crises, transformations, and metamorphoses, with the new emerging through a leap into existence." (Jaspers 2019 [1919], 311; my transl.) We undergo significant disruptions in life, but having resolved them for ourselves—at least to some degree and on several occasions—translates into a sense that we can master future challenges, even if it means becoming someone else; that is, even if we have to accept that certain—even central—views about ourselves must be relinquished to make space for a new self-understanding: "Yet it is precisely the spiritual that is unable to hold fast to essential knowledge—a knowledge that provides hold [Halt] and meaning to life as a whole—for everything is drawn into the swirling movement of infinite dialectic" (Jaspers 2019 [1919], 312; my transl.). He emphasizes that what bridges—and thereby holds together—times of disruption, when worldviews are shattered by events, is not knowledge but a kind of existential *faith*. This faith, he argues, is what makes knowledge possible in the first place and therefore cannot itself be reduced to knowledge. It provides hold amid uncertainty by anticipating resolution and clarification; a faith directed toward the world as a temporally unfolding process that attains determination only over time (Jaspers 2019 [1919], 312ff.).

I suggest that this can be applied to the case of self-familiarity and our narrative identities, which can be understood as forms of, or as belonging to, particular worldviews. However, as hinted at before, I propose that the confidence of self-familiarity is not always independent of one's previous experiences and of the knowledge that emerges from them. One may well be able to enact a kind of trust in the process *ex nihilo*, as it were—that is, even if one's life so far has been marked by chaos and confidence has not developed naturally. Even so, it strikes me as plausible to assume that confidence in the ongoing process of self-familiarization, at least *typically*, emerges out of—and, insofar as it is part of mediated self-familiarity—relies on experiences of familiarity which may be places, other people, practices, and the whole "integrated web of constituents I daily use to recollect a sense of myself" (Køster 2022, 6).

While this means that there are many resources in the world offering anchors for one's self-familiarization, it also implies a general vulnerability of the entire process. We can be disturbed in the development of confidence in the process of self-familiarization: our practical sense of the ability to make ourselves familiar with the world can be challenged both by the concrete

lifeworlds we inhabit and by our own psychological constitution. Before turning to how self-talk in BPD may factor into this, I wish to make one final point in my sketch of self-familiarity.

I have argued that self-familiarity goes beyond an epistemic or narrative self-relation and essentially involves a practical sense. I would now like to add that self-familiarity also has an intrinsic affective dimension, as it generally feels better to be at one with ourselves—to feel familiar with rather than alienated from ourselves. We prefer to have some grip on ourselves rather than to be confused about who we are. It is typically not a good feeling to sense that we are not truly being who we really are, that we are somehow failing to actualize our real being—even if we lack a clear view of who that is.

Confidence in the ongoing process of self-familiarization, by contrast, comes with a sense of security, control, and serenity, all of which are experiences that are typically considered to have a positive affective valence. It is no coincidence that Western philosophy has put such an emphasis on getting to know oneself as a path towards wisdom and happiness. For instance, the Stoic notion of *eudaimonia* involves a threefold association between (1) finding one's home in the *cosmos*, the world, that is, a meaningful role in the *logos*; (2) the ability to recalibrate one's identity and the values that constitute it depending on what is in our power to control; and (3), the positive, well-spirited future-directed attitude that is characterized through both confidence and serenity. Although Stoic *eudaimonia* is only a practical ideal—and one that would certainly require further discussion of normative issues—it nevertheless serves well to illustrate the point I wish to make: finding one's place in the world and becoming, to some degree, flexible with regard to one's narrative identities translates into a confidence in the ongoing process of self-familiarization. Such confidence, if it is absolute, as conceived in the ideal case of the Stoic sage, gives rise to a well-spirited mind that enjoys tranquility and a positive openness toward the future. As I will show in the next section, it is precisely the way self-talk manifests in BPD—constituting, as it were, inner demons—that can pose significant challenges to developing the well-spiritedness associated with self-familiarity.

2.3 'Linguistic shrapnel': How negative self-talk undermines self-familiarity in BPD

Although more empirical research is required to fully understand their phenomenology and role in the dynamics of BPD, the insights and evidence from the reviewed studies on intrapersonal plurality, auditory verbal hallucinations, and self-talk provide a valuable point of departure for exploring self-familiarity in BPD. The final section is devoted to this task. I begin with intrapersonal plurality.

2.3.1 Intrapersonal plurality in BPD: disorder of the dynamics of self-familiarization

When discussing intrapersonal plurality, it is important to emphasize that the mere existence of different aspects of personality—which may at times come into conflict with one another—is entirely common. It is reasonable to assume that most people occasionally experience inner conflict and have yet to develop a coherent stance on a given situation or issue. Goethe’s famous line, “Two souls, alas, dwell in my breast,” most likely expresses a fundamental aspect of the human condition. It has even been suggested that “some kinds of double consciousness (...) are worth preserving—not only because of the added richness they bring to our lives but also because of the added knowledge, flexibility, and empathy they provide” (Church 2021, 3). It would therefore be a mistake to regard the mere plurality of internal “voices” as the decisive problem in the self-experience of BPD. What seems more important is how these “voices”, or the sometimes mutually contradictory aspects of personality, are organized.

While the organization of various self-parts is likely to differ from one individual to another, the studies discussed on BPD have identified certain recurring tendencies. In addition to a general inclination toward a fragmented construction of identity, specific self-positions have been observed that are thematically associated with anger, helplessness, nihilistic detachment, coping attempts, or an idealized self. Crucially, these self-aspects are often in internal conflict with one another, which makes them difficult to integrate.

One possible explanation for this phenomenon is that negative emotions tend to have a segregating effect in themselves, hindering the formation of “meaning bridges” between different experiences (Stiles, 2011, 377). This might be so because emotions such as anger, helplessness, or nihilistic detachment are more likely to consume the entire self and its experience. Moreover, negative emotions not seldom spiral towards high affective intensities, which typically calls for all available attention and so leaves little space for the creation of specific meaningful connections with other self-states that seem irrelevant for the present urgent situation (Schmidt 2022, Schmidt 2020, Schmidt & Fuchs 2021). Instead, these self-states appear to dominate and override other, potentially more differentiated, self-states, without being integrated in an overall framework. Rather than fostering the essential flexibility needed to navigate between different self-states (Fisher et al. 2020), a predominantly passive succession of seemingly isolated self-states emerges that tend to be perceived as chaotic and disruptive, and, therefore, as incomprehensible.

Even when individuals remember narrative facts and events, these do not necessarily coalesce into a cohesive narrative identity capable of fostering a sense of self-familiarity. According to the assimilation model, a meaningful connection—what Stiles (2011, 377) calls “meaning bridges”—between various self-states or internal voices requires that these states be “mutually accessible”. However, in moments of intense anger, frustration, hopelessness, or emptiness, other self-parts are often inaccessible. Even when they are remembered, the ability to empathize with these other self-states is inhibited by the urgency of the prevailing negative emotions. These self-states, therefore, challenge what Schechtman (2001) has famously described as a crucial “ingredient” in the construction of narrative identity: “empathic access”. It is, in fact, plausible to suggest that such negative affect makes opposing self-states—such as those associated with happiness, harmony, or relaxation—feel distant, alien, and even impossible for oneself. While one might be aware that a version of oneself has been happy or relaxed before, one’s present self may lack a sense of “affective familiarity” (Ratcliffe 2004) with the remembered self and thus lose the feeling of being, or having been, that past self.

From this follows the idea that strong negative emotions possess not only a disruptive but also a dissociative tendency. A general sense of emptiness, which often constitutes a dominant self-state in BPD, similarly prevents individuals from experiencing their remembered self-parts as familiar. Instead, this emptiness is characterized by the inaccessibility and unfamiliarity of other self-states. Both negative affect and persistent feelings of emptiness bring the internal dialogue—metaphorically speaking—between the various self-parts of an individual almost to a standstill. Alternatively, this dialogue may remain locked in irresolvable tension, as the inner conflict fails to establish familiarity between the person’s internal voices. It is likely that this results in an excruciating sense of being torn between conflicting impulses that are difficult to reconcile, leaving the individual feeling helpless and overwhelmed, which may contribute to recurring feelings of “desperate vitality” (Stanghellini & Rosfort 2013) that have been associated with BPD.

From this, I take it that the intensity and valence of the emotions typical of BPD are accompanied by an inner conversational mode that does not facilitate the integration of intrapersonal plurality. Consequently, self-familiarization does not occur, even when certain processes or patterns may reappear with a sense of familiarity—namely, the feeling that one has already been in a similar kind of situation. My suggestion, therefore, is to conceptualize self-disturbance in BPD less as a straightforward lack of a sense of identity and more as a disruption of the fundamental processes of ongoing self-familiarization, resulting in a disorganization of intrapersonal plurality. This

perspective can be further illustrated by examining internal dialogues not only in a *metaphorical* sense but also in their more specific, *literal* form.

2.3.2 Inner speech in BPD: self-invalidation challenges self-familiarization

The studies referenced in the literature review provide significant insights, particularly concerning self-critical voices that represent a continuous and recurring form of self-invalidation. Given the numerous mentions of such phenomena, it can be assumed that the presence of an inner critic is a common form of inner speech in the context of BPD. This inner critic often reflects the lingering impact of traumatic experiences—especially the internalized voices of parents or close caregivers—which are sometimes perceived as hostile. The philosopher Denise Riley aptly described this phenomenon as “linguistic shrapnel” (Riley 2005, 19): negative experiences and the words of others become detached from their original contexts and come to dominate an individual’s inner speech. Over time, they evolve into a persistently harsh attitude toward oneself, expressed through linguistic fragments. Initially appearing as fleeting thoughts or traces, these fragments embed themselves into one’s experience, gradually shaping overall perception or persisting as a constant, disruptive undercurrent in the background.

What is the impact of such a linguistically structured inner wound on the process of self-familiarization?

First, I would like to highlight an important implication of repeated inner self-criticism: the absence of positive self-affirmation. The search for meaning and the question of who one is are universal tasks that all individuals must navigate and resolve for themselves. Regular positive experiences play a crucial role in this process (Lyubomirsky, King, & Diener 2005). It is the moments of small joys that reaffirm what is meaningful to us in life—where we find fulfillment and, by extension, who we are. In these moments, we feel addressed by life and, in a sense, touched or “met” in our individuality. Ultimately, it is precisely these moments that foster a sense of familiarity with ourselves. However, as one of the cited studies observed, individuals with BPD often experience self-critical inner speech precisely when they are having positive experiences (Koivisto et al. 2021b, 927). These self-punishing voices undermine positive emotions that would otherwise serve as an important source of self-affirmation.

Second, regular positive experiences also provide us with a sense of control over our lives. While not all feelings of happiness must arise from our own actions, many moments of fulfillment do give rise to the sense that we are capable of navigating and mastering life with all its challenges—that, in a sense, we are on the right path. Stoic philosophy, with its concept of *ephe*’

hêmin (“what is up to us”) (Epictetus 2008, Discourses, I.1), has long emphasized the close relationship between what lies within our power and our true self. While this metaphysical perspective extends beyond the scope of the present discussion, it aptly underscores the idea that a sense of control significantly contributes to self-familiarity and is essential for the process of self-familiarization. From this perspective, it is not enough for certain experiences simply to recur in order to develop a sense of self-familiarity. Familiarity with recurring situations—often observed in the context of BPD—does not suffice to foster a deeper sense of self-familiarity. Rather, it is precisely the feeling of being merely exposed to life, to others, and to circumstances—without the ability to influence these processes in the ways one would like—that decisively undermines self-familiarity. A significant factor here is the habitual self-invalidation exhibited by individuals with BPD, often enacted through self-talk. Even in positive moments, the sudden emergence of self-punishing thoughts can create a pervasive sense of helplessness: no matter what one does, the internal dialogue persistently casts doubt on one’s actions, desires, and feelings, questioning their legitimacy. This, in turn, makes it exceedingly difficult to stand by one’s aspirations and to identify with them.

This becomes clearer when considering that, thirdly, self-punitive voices also contribute to low self-esteem. Those who do not feel worthy of themselves or who mistrust their own experiences are less likely to find grounding in them and to develop a stable sense of self. Self-identification with what one appears to be becomes more difficult when one’s own experiences are dismissed as invalid. Furthermore, low self-esteem is often accompanied by an intense experience of an ideal self—a concept that has also been identified as one of the typical self-states in the context of BPD. The ideal self appears to function as a projection of the true self that one *could* or *should* be, but ultimately *is* not. Implicitly constructed through negative self-talk, this ideal self likely exacerbates the inner division between various self-aspects that are in tension with one another and that struggle to become familiar or integrated with each other. The construction of an unreachable ideal self through negative inner speech thus gives rise to the sense of failing to realize one’s supposed true self.

Furthermore, it is worth recalling that, *fourth*, self-talk plays a significant role in general self-regulation (Kross et al., 2014). For individuals who struggle to manage their emotions and thoughts due to uncontrollable inner speech, it becomes correspondingly more difficult to navigate their self-states. We are all constantly subject to significant shifts of state—for instance, when making a decision and having to overcome emerging opposing impulses through willpower. In many cases, self-talk likely plays a supportive role in this process, as it helps preserve the dominant voice in inner speech from distractions, thereby contributing to the formation of a

perceived central core of the self. Through inner speech, a particular “self” carries itself across time and through the ever-changing experiences of life.

A decision made with full vitality to pursue a specific goal may, over time, come to feel alien due to growing fatigue and difficulty, leading to a decline in motivation. Self-talk often functions as an important means of recalling the original intention, renewing its motivating force, and preserving self-familiarity with the decision until the intention is fulfilled. When training for a marathon, for example, the body may feel utterly unwilling to continue running; yet the self of the decision—still present in inner speech—drives one to new heights of performance. The motivational significance of self-talk for athletic achievement is well documented (Hatzigeorgiadis et al. 2011), and, as I want to suggest, it may also apply to the general persistence of self-aspects over time.

From this perspective, self-talk provides a means of becoming aware of prior self-states and maintaining a connection to them, especially when immediate impressions and situational feelings might otherwise prompt a shift in self-orientation. The close relationship between self-knowledge or self-awareness and self-talk has been repeatedly emphasized from a theoretical standpoint (Rovetta 2025, Wilkinson 2020, Morin 1993). While further empirical research into these connections and their underlying mechanisms is needed, it can be speculated that negative self-talk in BPD undermines this identity-preserving function of inner speech.

Fifth, further ways in which inner speech phenomena may undermine self-familiarity arise from the specific linguistic dimensions inherent to them. These include, for instance, the speaking voice (who is talking?) and the intended addressee (to whom is the voice speaking?). While such aspects likely vary individually and call for further empirical investigation, the cases discussed in the aforementioned studies illustrate how particular configurations of inner speech can negatively affect self-familiarity. In one case, for example, the individual was unable to clearly identify which version of the self the inner voice was addressing, making immediate identification with the addressee impossible (Edwards 2016, 148). In other cases, punitive voices internalized as parental figures compelled the adult individual to assume the position of a child (Koivisto 2021b, 926). This, too, can be understood as producing an inner rupture that undermines the cohesion of different self-aspects. Assuming the mental stance of a child is likely to conflict with the various roles an adult occupies in everyday life—such as those in professional contexts, partnerships, or social circles—thereby fostering experiences of alienation.

Finally, auditory verbal hallucinations (AVHs) should not go unmentioned. Studies on this phenomenon suggest that AVHs in the context of BPD resemble those observed in schizophrenia. Notably, the precise phenomenal character of such experiences is difficult to categorize. While the perceived voices seem to possess a quasi-perceptual quality, they do not fit neatly within the category of auditory hallucinations understood as faulty perception. It is likely that even for those who experience AVHs, the exact mode of this “being affected”—a paradoxical “hearing without hearing” (Ratcliffe 2017, 63)—remains unclear, spanning multiple spectra: between belief and perception, and between activity and passivity. Setting aside the specific content of these voices, one may assume that such an ambiguous experiential mode, which neither allows for control nor finds intersubjective validation, further undermines familiarity with oneself and confidence in the ongoing process of self-familiarization.

Conclusion

Human experience is profoundly shaped by language and its underlying structures. Experiencing inner monologues or dialogues in everyday life is by no means unusual. Much of our thinking—and, by extension, our self-realization as experiencing agents—takes place through inner speech. Through this medium, we navigate our emotions, desires, and thoughts, forming evaluations, decisions, judgments, and resolutions that guide our actions. When we engage in internal dialogue, we negotiate the diverse interests and impulses that correspond to different facets of our personality. Inner speech thus serves as a medium through which the various parts of the self come into contact with one another, fostering self-familiarity, organizing aspects of our being, and structuring the self as a central and unifying instance.

The insight that our individual existence may be inherently plural—meaning that the self is constituted by aspects that can, in principle, come into conflict and require the resolution of ambivalence and decision-making in certain situations—likely resonates with many people. From this perspective, identity is not a monolithic entity that, once discovered, remains stable over time. Rather, as I have proposed here, it is an ongoing process of self-familiarization, concerning the development, maintenance, and continual actualization of one’s self-understanding. As I have further suggested, self-familiarity extends beyond a merely epistemic, narrative, or affective relation to oneself; it also entails a practical sense of being able to renew and sustain a self with which one feels at one, even in the face of transformative events and unforeseen situations. This also implies that self-familiarity comes in degrees and depends on one’s individual capacity for self-familiarization.

According to the hypothesis developed here—and to be explored further empirically—if the process of self-familiarization is disrupted, confidence in it can be severely undermined, resulting in a diminished sense of self-familiarity. In the case of BPD, self-familiarity—or a sense of self—is not entirely absent, as individuals often report that they repeatedly find themselves in the same kinds of situations and feel caught in a process that cannot be transcended. What is lacking, however, is precisely the confidence in the process of self-familiarization: they lack the practical capacity to bring about a feeling of being at one with themselves, despite their awareness of certain narrative facts or of different self-aspects.

The studies reviewed here suggest that the way inner speech manifests in individuals with borderline personality disorder (BPD) may play a significant role in weakening this sense of capacity. In my interpretation, the self-states typically associated with BPD—such as anger, powerlessness, and detachment—tend to resist the integration and acknowledgment of other aspects of the self. This aligns with the observation that intrapersonal plurality is difficult to tolerate in BPD, often resulting in the dissolution of plurality in favor of a single dominant self-state. Yet such unidimensional identities, which suppress other central parts of the self, are typically unsustainable in the long run, as is frequently observed in individuals with BPD. These challenges to self-familiarization in BPD emerge at the most fundamental level of the dialogical structures of human experience—even when verbal elements, in the stricter sense of language, do not necessarily play a role in the process.

By contrast, when individuals with BPD engage in self-talk in the *literal* sense, it often takes the form of self-invalidation, manifesting as an inner critic. As argued in this article, such self-talk can further severely impede the ongoing process of self-familiarization, likely contributing to the self-instability frequently observed in BPD. An important question for future research concerns how self-invalidation through negative self-talk in BPD relates to self-criticism in other mental health conditions—such as depression—where self-critical views also play a central role in self-experience, yet are not typically associated with the same volatility of identity observed in BPD. Identifying the factors that explain these differential effects of negative self-talk on the process of self-familiarization will, I suggest, be highly informative for further characterizing, understanding, and differentiating diverse mental health conditions. Such comparative analyses may also shed light on the broader mechanisms through which self-directed language shapes the stability or fragility of self-experience across different psychopathological profiles.

For instance, although the same degree of self-instability may not be present in depression as in BPD, I hypothesize that self-criticism in inner speech still significantly shapes self-experience in

depression. Rather than destroying any attempt at a positive self-view, as often occurs in BPD, depressive self-criticism operates by petrifying a negative identity, rendering any prospect of a renewed self futile from the outset. Depressive self-criticism, then, can also be understood as a disturbance in the process of self-familiarization—one in which confidence in one’s practical capacity to make oneself at home in the world is persistently undermined. While in depression a relatively stable, albeit negative, sense of identity may crystallize, individuals with depression do not experience genuine self-familiarity, for the kind of self they feel compelled to embody appears strange, alien, and not truly their own. Elaborating this hypothesis in greater detail will be the subject of future work.

Understanding volatility in self-perception as a disturbance of self-familiarization mediated by negative self-talk underscores the significance of self-talk as a potential focus for intervention in BPD recovery. While self-talk has been recognized as an important therapeutic tool in the treatment of BPD and related mental health conditions (Kellogg & Garcia Torres 2021, Kelly et al. 2009, Linehan 1993), further research is needed to explore how individuals can structure their internal dialogues and improve the ways they speak to themselves. Given that self-talk in BPD often proves counterproductive—exacerbating self-alienation rather than fostering self-integration—more detailed guidance and tailored interventions may be required to help individuals unlock the salutogenic potential of self-talk (Kross et al. 2014).

Inner speech encompasses both passive-receptive and active-agentive phenomena, representing a domain of experience in which self-control can either be effectively exercised or devolve into powerlessness when dialogical self-regulation fails. Empowering individuals with BPD to cultivate (self-)dialogical competencies may therefore be a crucial step in transforming a predominantly passive mode of experience into a more active and engaged one. Such transformation could help individuals establish and nurture their own voices and, in doing so, regain a grounding that fosters self-familiarization. Insights into these processes may also prove highly relevant to recent debates on self-illness ambiguity (Dings & de Bruin 2023).

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